

Research

A theoretical analysis of the influence of time of day and weather conditions on the metro passenger arrival volume utilizing a multiple linear regression model

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Abstract: The metropolitan transit system is a critical component of urban transportation, offering a fast, reliable, and environmentally friendly mode of travel in densely populated cities. This research delves into the factors influencing metro passengers' arrival volumes at Yujiatou Station on Wuhan Metro Line 5 in China, focusing on the influence of time of day and weather conditions. The study addresses a significant research gap in understanding metro passengers' dynamics by utilizing questionnaires, direct field observation, and statistical techniques, including multiple linear regression for data analysis. The results revealed meaningful relationships, such as a strong correlation between rainy evening weather and arrival volumes and a mode volume positive correlation between time of day and arrival volumes. The model demonstrated a reasonable fit for capturing these relationships. The study also highlights the individual impacts of weather and time of day on predicting metro passenger arrival volumes. The research suggests that adjusting service schedules based on weather conditions and peak times could help manage passenger flow, which has practical implications for transportation planners, metro operators, and passengers, informing strategies for optimizing service schedules and enhancing the overall user experience. These findings can contribute to sustainable transportation initiatives and urban development goals by improving urban transportation systems.

Keywords: Metro Passenger Arrival volume; Multiple Linear Regression; Influencing Factor Analysis; Wuhan Metro Line 5; Yujiatou Station.

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Introduction

The urban metro transit system has been recognized as an efficacious modality for mitigating vehicular congestion. This acknowledgment stems from its exemplary attributes, including reliability, punctuality, energy efficiency, and the ability to accommodate many passengers. It also plays a vital role in advancing significant cities' economic, environmental, and social objectives [1], [2]. A well-functioning public transportation system that delivers exceptional

service is pivotal in attracting more passengers [3]. This article investigates the influence of weather conditions and time of day on metro passenger arrivals, shedding light on their significance in metro planning and enhancing passenger satisfaction. Specifically, the study explores the impact of weather conditions and time of day on metro passenger arrival volumes. By delving into these aspects, we aim to deepen our comprehension of the factors shaping metro passenger behavior and guide the development of strategies to optimize metro services and better cater to passengers' needs. The volume of passenger arrivals is affected by the time of day, dividing passengers into two categories: those who adhere to the timetable and those who do not. Analysis of recorded passenger arrival volumes demonstrates fluctuations in the percentage of passengers depending on the timeline at different times of the day, including morning, evening, and off-peak hours [4]. Passenger behavior and arrival patterns vary significantly throughout the day, influenced by work schedules and availability of leisure time [5]. Weather conditions also play a significant role, with warm weather boosting ridership and cold, windy conditions reducing transportation use [6]. Research on metro ridership in Nanjing found that weather affects weekend travelers more than weekday travelers [7]. Train frequency strongly influences passenger arrival patterns, impacting wait times and station congestion [8], [9]. Higher train frequency leads to more random passenger arrivals, while lower frequency causes passengers to strategically time their arrivals to minimize wait times [10]. Passenger behavior significantly influences arrival patterns, categorized into those who follow schedules and those who arrive unpredictably [11]. Various statistical distributions, including lognormal and gamma distributions, have been used to model arrival patterns [12]. However, numerous passengers in bustling stations often endure prolonged wait times beyond their expected platform wait duration, posing a challenge at crowded stations and impacting passenger satisfaction and behavior [13]. Although peak-hour travelers typically encounter shorter wait times, overcrowding at origin stations may cause extended waits [10]. While traditional passenger waiting time estimation relied on field observations, recent advancements have introduced intelligent card data for more precise estimates [14]. Unforeseeable headways can lead to longer wait times and congestion at stations during passenger boarding and alighting, prompting the proposal of headway management systems to mitigate demand fluctuations and minimize wait time variability [15], [16]. Furthermore, optimizing the Metro system requires balancing meeting passenger needs and ensuring operational efficiency [17]. Fixed train timetables may not effectively address variable demand, necessitating approaches like mixed-integer linear programming for optimal scheduling [18].

Research Methodology

This research aimed to explore the influence of meteorological conditions and time of days on metro passenger arrival volumes. A questionnaire-based methodology was employed to capture real-time data concerning commuter demographics, travel patterns, subjective meteorological conditions, and travel time. This approach was predicated on the prerequisite that respondents were frequent users of Metro line 5 and possessed proficiency in English, as the survey was disseminated in this language. This criterion was essential to ensure that participants could accurately comprehend and respond to the survey questions. A dataset comprising 199 responses was systematically gathered utilizing a questionnaire method within the confines of the Yujiatou Campus, part of Wuhan University of Technology, located in Wuhan City. This location was chosen strategically due to its immediate adjacency to the Yujiatou metro station, a critical node along metro line 5. The determination of this sample size was grounded in achieving an 80% statistical power to identify differences in metro passenger arrival volumes attributable to either weather or diurnal variations, with a significance threshold set at 0.05, indicating that observed differences with a probability of occurring by chance less than 5% were considered statistically significant. Convenience sampling was utilized for respondent selection, facilitating data collection across varied timeframes and meteorological conditions over one month. Additionally, due to the lack of Automatic Fare Collection data, a direct field observation of passenger arrival volumes was conducted at Yujiatou, Qingnian Road, and Jiangshe 2nd Road stations in Wuhan. Moreover, initial quality control measures were implemented to ensure the integrity and reliability of the collected data. Preliminary questionnaires were distributed to a select group of 13 respondents to evaluate their comprehension of the survey questions through a

reliability analysis. This analysis employed Cronbach's alpha statistic to ascertain the internal consistency and reliability of the survey items or scales. Following this methodology, the variable representing the time of day exhibited modevolume internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.518$) across two items. In contrast, the variable for passenger arrival volumes displayed high internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.887$) across six items. The meteorological conditions variable showed modevolume internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.615$) with two items. Nonetheless, the dataset underwent transformation via an inverse distribution function known as the quantile function or quantile mapping. This transformation process was bifurcated into two stages: initially, fractional ranks were produced for each variable's dataset, followed by a transformation utilizing the inverse distribution function for each variable in response to deviations from normal distribution. In addition to using descriptive statistical techniques such as frequency counts and standard deviation to summarize the characteristics of the collected data, we will employ inferential statistical tests like correlation analysis and multiple regression analysis to analyze the impact of weather conditions and time of day on metro passenger arrival volumes. While our sample size is insufficient for this study, it's essential to recognize the potential limitations in generalizing findings to all metro lines in Wuhan City and other cities. Furthermore, creating a Chinese questionnaire is necessary as most Line 5 users may need to be proficient in English, potentially allowing for a larger sample size. Additionally, utilizing Automatic Fare Collection data instead of manual data is recommended.

Results

Direct Field Observation of Metro Passengers Arrival Volume

We conducted a six-week observation of passenger arrival volumes at three stations in Wuhan, collecting data at different times of the day. We also gathered temperature measurements. Our systematic approach allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of passenger arrival volumes, focusing on morning, off-peak, and evening hours. This data is presented in the table and figures provided below. For a comprehensive view of the entire dataset, which includes all stations and specific time intervals, please refer to the Appendix A.

Table 1. Summary of Metro Passenger Flow Observations

Station	Time Period	Highest Passenger Count	Lowest Passenger Count	Remarks
Yujiatou	Morning (Week 1)	Peak 1,754 (Monday)	407 (Sunday)	Highest on Monday, sharp drop on weekends.
	Evening (Week 4)	Peak 1,257 (Friday)	653 (Sunday)	Friday peak, with gradual decline toward Sunday.
Qingnian Road	Morning (Week 5)	Peak 1,670 (Monday, Friday)	490 (Sunday)	Consistent high on weekdays, lowest on Sunday.
	Evening (Week 5)	Peak 2,041 (Friday)	1,134 (Saturday)	Highest passenger flow on Friday evening.
Jiangshe 2nd Rd	Morning (Week 6)	Peak 1,131 (Monday)	613 (Sunday)	Higher weekday traffic, Sunday low.
	Off-Peak (Week 6)	624 (Saturday)	555 (Wednesday)	Off-peak hours show relatively consistent traffic.

Figure 1. Weekdays & Weekends Metro Passenger Arrival Volume for both Week 1 & Week 2

The pie charts in **Figure 1**. Show that weekday passenger volumes are consistently higher than weekends, reflecting typical commuter patterns. During summer holidays, more off-peak hour travel on weekends indicates increased leisure travel. This highlights the impact of summer holidays on metro travel patterns, with heightened off-peak and weekend travel volumes due to non-commuter activities.

Figure 2. Weekdays & Weekends Metro Passenger Arrival Volume for both Week 3 & Week 4

Figure 2. Shows that In July 2023, there was increased off-peak hour and weekend travel, indicating more leisure travel due to school closures and vacations. In May 2024, there were dominant weekday morning peak hours and increased evening peak hour travel, suggesting more evening activities or later commutes.

Figure 3. Weekdays & Weekends Metro Passenger Arrival Volume for both Week 5 & Week 6

The figure above shows typical weekdays at the Qingnian Road Station. The higher percentage of evening peak hour dominance suggests that many commuters used this station to return home from work or school. In contrast, the lower off-peak percentage indicates that the station primarily serves as a hub for commuting, with less leisure or non-work-related travel occurring during the middle of the day. Compared to the Qingnian Road Station, the Jiangshe 2nd Road Station I had a noticeable increase in off-peak travel during weekends. A higher off-peak percentage on weekends indicates more leisure travel, with individuals using the station for activities such as shopping, dining, or visiting friends and family. However, evening peak hours remained dominant, suggesting significant evening activity.

Demographic Distribution

Table 2. Below provides a descriptive overview of the socio-demographic in this study. A total of 199 valid responses are collected, and the target audience are within Wuhan Metro Line 5. Among the participants, 48.2% were male, and 51.8 % were female. In terms of educational background, 18.1% of the participants are identified as high school students, while the 45.7% identify as bachelor, 27.6% as master student while the remaining 8.6% are doctovolume.

Table 2. Demographic Distribution

Variable	Code	Description	N	Percentage %
Demographic Distribution	Gender	MALE	96	48.2
		FEMALE	103	51.8
	Educational level	highschoolorbelow	36	18.1
		bachelor	91	45.7
		master	55	27.6
doctovolume		17	8.6	

Correlation Analysis

A statistically significant correlation was found between passenger arrival volume and time of day, with a significant positive link shown by $r(199) = 0.229^{**}$, $p < 0.001$. There was a strong positive relationship between passenger arrival volume and weather, with a correlation coefficient of 0.597 and a statistically significant p-value of less than 0.001. The relationship between the time of day and weather was not statistically significant, with a correlation coefficient of 0.050 and a p-value of 0.487. The results indicate that the volume of passenger arrivals is correlated with both the time of day and the weather conditions. As presented in the **Table 3**. Below.

Table 3. Correlation results

		TOD	PAR	WTH
TOD	Pearson Correlation	1	0.229**	0.050
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.001	0.487
	N	199		
PAR	Pearson Correlation	0.229**	1	0.597**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001		0
	N	199		
WTH	Pearson Correlation	0.050	0.597**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.487	0.000	
	N	199		

Note: PAR = Passenger arrival volume, TOD = Time of day, WTH = Weather, Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

A multiple linear regression analysis was performed using SPSS to create a regression model aimed at predicting metro passenger arrival volumes, while taking into consideration the independent variables such as time of day and weather. The results of the regression model indicated an R-squared value of around 0.40, signifying that the combination of weather and time of day may explain approximately 40% of the variability in the dependent variable, which is passenger arrival volume. These results are detailed in **Table 4** below.

Table 4. Model Summary results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.629 ^a	0.396	0.390	0.43389

Note: Predictors: (Constant), Time of day and the Weather, Dependent Variable: Passenger Arrival volume. However, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to assess the significance of the regression model predicting passenger arrival volume based on the independent variables weather, time of day. The following results were obtained: The result indicate a highly significant regression model ($F = 64.197$, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that the independent variables (time of day, weather) have a collective significant effect on the dependent variable (passenger arrival volume). As presented in the **Table 5**. Below.

Table 5. ANOVA results

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.172	2	12.086	64.197	0.000 ^b
	Residual	36.900	196	0.188		
	Total	61.072	198			

- a. Dependent Variable: PAR (Passenger arrival volume)
- b. Predictors: (Constant), WTH (Weather), TOD (Time of day)

However, the estimated coefficients for the model **Table 6**, provide the insight into the individual contribution of time of day and the weather to the predicted metro passenger’s arrival volume. The following results were obtained: The

constant term had an unstandardized coefficient ($B = -0.163$, $p = 0.341$), which holds a limited significance, representing the theoretical arrival volume when both time of day and weather are zero. Moreover, the unstandardized coefficient for time of day (TOD) was ($B = 0.181$, $p = 0.000$) indicating that for each unit increase in time of day (TOD), the predicted metro arrival volume increase by 0.181 units, the positive coefficient indicate that higher metro passenger arrival occur during the day. Similarly, weather (WTH) had an unstandardized coefficient ($B = 0.794$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that for each unit increase in weather (WTH), the predicted metro passenger arrival volume increase by 0.794 units, the positive coefficient suggest a notable impact of favorable weather condition on metro passenger arrival volume.

Table 6. Coefficients Estimate Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-0.163	0.171		-0.954	0.341
	TOD	0.181	0.051	0.200	3.590	0.000
	WTH	0.794	0.075	0.587	10.556	0.000

Note: Dependent Variable: Passenger Arrival volume, $p < 0.01$

Fig 4. Scatterplot and histogram for the dependent variable

Discussion

During the field observation at the Yujiatou, Jiangshe 2nd Road line 5, and Qingnian Road line 2 in Wuhan, there were distinct patterns in passenger arrival volumes across different times of the day and weather conditions. On weekdays, morning and evening peak hours consistently showed higher passenger volumes than off-peak hours, reflecting typical commuter patterns. Visual representations in Figures 1, 2, and 3 indicate the proportion of passenger volume at different times of the day, categorized by weekdays and weekends for each week. The data consistently showed that passenger volumes on weekdays were more significant than on weekends, reflecting typical commuter patterns. In July 2023, during the summer vacation, there was an increase in off-peak hour travel on weekends, indicating more leisure travel. In May 2024, not coinciding with the peak holiday season, there was a more balanced distribution of travel times, with a noticeable increase in evening peak hour travel compared to July 2023. This is in line with the findings of previous studies [5] and [7]. The analysis revealed a substantial and statistically significant positive correlation (0.597^{**} , $p < 0.01$) between weather conditions and metro passenger arrival volumes, as detailed in Table 3. This suggests that factors such as evening rainfall have a favorable impact on metro passenger arrivals, consistent with the findings in Table 1 and the earlier study [6]. Additionally, the data in Table 3 indicates that there is no discernible relationship between weather and the time of day, with a correlation coefficient of 0.050 and a significance level of $p > 0.01$. This suggests that the time of day does not have a direct influence on weather, and vice versa. The regression models were created using multiple

linear regression analysis to forecast the arrival volume of metro passengers. The results in Table 4 indicate that both time of day and weather may explain around 40% of the variation in metro passenger arrival volume, suggesting the presence of other influential factors not accounted for by the model, which are particularly crucial in transportation planning and management. Furthermore, the ANOVA results from Table 5 distinctly demonstrate the significance of the regression model in predicting metro passenger arrival volume based on independent variables such as weather and time of day. The F-statistics from the residual analysis (64.197, $p < 0.01$) suggest that the model significantly fits the metro passenger arrival volume prediction. Moreover, the independent variables, time of day and weather, collectively significantly impact the dependent variable, metro passenger arrival volume. Moreover, the coefficient estimate in Table 6 distinctly shows the individual influence of time of day and weather on the expected metro passenger arrival volume. This indicates that the predicted metro passenger arrival volume increases by 0.181 units with a unit increase in time of day, suggesting that higher metro passenger arrivals may typically occur during morning and evening peak hours, consistent with the manually collected data in Table 1 and a previous study [12]. Similarly, the expected metro passenger arrival volume increases by 0.794 units with a unit increase in weather conditions, suggesting that a decrease in metro passenger arrivals may occur due to various weather conditions, such as evening rain. These insights are essential for planning, managing passenger flow, and improving user experiences, potentially contributing to urban transportation sustainability and development goals. To develop a more resilient and customer-focused metro transit system that can accommodate the various and changing needs of passengers during different times of the day and in various weather conditions, policymakers need to take into account the following strategies to improve the effectiveness and dependability of metro systems:

- (1) To disperse passenger demand and reduce traffic congestion during peak hours, targeted advertising and fare discounts could be introduced to promote travel during non-peak times. By offering incentives for off-peak travel, transportation officials can maximize metro capacity, minimize congestion, and improve overall network efficiency.
- (2) It is also essential to integrate weather data into service planning to anticipate and mitigate the impact of weather on passenger behavior.
- (3) Additionally, ongoing research should be conducted to identify and understand other variables influencing passenger arrival volumes, allowing for continuous improvement of metro services.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study aimed to investigate the influence of time of day and weather on metro passenger arrival volumes, uncovering valuable insights that contribute both theoretically and practically to the understanding of factors impacting metro systems. It, however, highlighted the importance of considering seasonal preferences and weather conditions in urban transportation planning, addressing a critical gap in understanding passenger behavior, while providing actionable recommendations for optimizing metro services, scheduling, and resource allocation.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Table A1 Direct Field Observation of Metro Passenger Flow

Date: 15th -21st May 2023 (Week 1)

Yujiatou Station

Weekdays	Weekends						
Morning peak hour							
Weather	23 ^o c/Fair	24 ^o c/cloud y	22 ^o c/Heav y rainfall	22 ^o c/Fair	24 ^o c/Fair	24 ^o c/Fog	24 ^o c/Fair
Time interval	Mon.	Tue.	Wed.	Thurs.	Fri.	Sat.	Sun.
7:00am-7:20am	420	422	200	394	450	195	103
7:20am-7:40am	573	547	350	552	539	247	149
7:40 am-8:00 am	761	624	360	582	457	300	155
Total	1754	1593	910	1528	1446	742	407
Off-peak hour							
	30 ^o c/cloud y	24 ^o c/cloud y	24 ^o c/cloud y	29 ^o c/Fair	29 ^o c/Sunn y	27 ^o c/Sunn y	26 ^o c/Light rain
12:00pm-12:20pm	129	77	80	120	110	240	125
12:20pm-12:40pm	87	147	110	93	123	158	90
12:40pm-01:00pm	104	128	106	128	108	203	192
Total	320	352	296	341	341	601	407
Evening peak hour							
	23 ^o c/cloud y	28 ^o c/rainfa l	24 ^o c/Fair	31 ^o c/Sunn y	30 ^o c/Sunn y	29 ^o c/Sunn y	24 ^o c/Cloud y
05:00pm-05:20pm	287	284	275	311	421	330	203
05:20pm-05:40pm	229	286	272	319	433	297	208
05:40pm-06:00pm	336	167	220	267	403	324	309
Total	852	737	767	897	1257	951	720

Date:10th -16thJuly
2023

Week 2

Weekdays

Weekends

Morning peak hour

Weather	30 ^o c/Sunny	33 ^o c/sunny	33 ^o c/sunny	33 ^o c/sunny	28 ^o c/sunny	30 ^o c/sunny	28 ^o c/fair
Time interval	Mon.	Tue.	Wed.	Thurs.	Fri.	Sat.	Sun.
8:00 am -8:20am	615	526	495	503	562	289	162

Off-peak hour

	30 ^o c/sunny	36 ^o c/sunny	36 ^o c/sunny	36 ^o c/sunny	28 ^o c/Sunny	32 ^o c/fair	31 ^o c/fair
12:00pm -12:20pm	105	81	87	95	113	145	119

Evening peak hour

	30 ^o c/sunny	36 ^o c/sunny	37 ^o c/sunny	35 ^o c/sunny	26 ^o c/Fair	32 ^o c/fair	31 ^o c/fair
06:00pm -06:20pm	287	272	247	244	307	225	160

Date: 17th-24thJuly 2023

Week 3

Weekdays

Weekends

Morning peak hour

Temperature	27 ^o c/Partly cloud	28 ^o c/Partly cloud	28 ^o c/fair	28 ^o c/ light rain	29 ^o c/Partly cloud	28 ^o c/cloud	28 ^o c/sunny
Time interval	Mon.	Tue.	Wed.	Thurs.	Fri.	Sat.	Sun.
8:00 am -8:20am	527	501	478	548	525	197	159

Off-peak hour

Temperature	30 ^o c/Partly cloud	31 ^o c/Partly cloud	30 ^o c/light rain	30 ^o c/Partly cloud	33 ^o c/sunny	29 ^o c/Partly cloud	33 ^o c/Partly cloud
12:00pm -12:20pm	94	110	95	89	80	159	132

Evening peak hour

Temperature	30 ^o c/fair	29 ^o c/Heavy rain	27 ^o c/Heavy rain	28 ^o c/Heavy rain	29 ^o c/cloud	32 ^o c/cloud	34 ^o c/Partly cloud
06:00pm -06:20pm	245	234	223	195	307	246	230

Date: 20th -26th May 2024

(Week 4)

Weekdays

Weekends

Morning peak hour

Weather	24 ^o c/Fair	24 ^o c/cloudy	22 ^o c/Heavy rainfall	24 ^o c/Fair	26 ^o c/Fair	24 ^o c/Fog	27 ^o c/Fair
Time interval	Mon.	Tue.	Wed.	Thurs.	Fri.	Sat.	Sun.
7:00am-7:20am	339	295	274	312	289	186	126
7:20am-7:40am	454	439	338	437	419	226	159
7:40 am-8:00 am	638	550	483	580	467	245	175
Total	1431	1238	1095	1329	1446	657	460

Off-peak hour

	27 ^o c/fair	24 ^o c/cloudy	24 ^o c/cloudy	27 ^o c/Fair	27 ^o c/Sunny	27 ^o c/Sunny	33 ^o c/partly cloud
12:00pm-12:20pm	148	201	130	79	116	185	162
12:20pm-12:40pm	132	133	127	90	128	167	160
12:40pm-01:00pm	127	133	138	100	113	193	185

Total	407	467	395	269	357	545	507
Evening peak hour							
	27°c/cloudy	28°c/ cloudy	27°c/Fair	31°c/Su nny	32°c/Sun ny	29°c/Sunny	33°c/Cloudy
05:00pm-05:20pm	291	297	245	326	287	265	230
05:20pm-05:40pm	241	296	237	466	277	289	208
05:40pm-06:00pm	283	326	321	437	354	287	215
Total	815	919	803	1229	1257	841	653

Date: 27th May-02 June 2024

(Week 5)

Qingnian Road Station

Weekdays

Weekends

Morning peak hour							
Weather	23°c/cloudy	21°c/cloudy	23°c/sunn y	19°c/light rain	21°c/Fo g	23°c/clear	24°c/su nny
Time interval	Mon.	Tue.	Wed.	Thurs.	Fri.	Sat.	Sun.
7:00am-7:20am	380	340	320	215	450	220	130
7:20am-7:40am	500	470	380	246	590	280	170
7:40 am-8:00 am	790	850	520	480	630	340	190
Total	1670	1660	1230	941	1670	840	490

Off-peak hour							
	28°c/sunny	28°c/cloudy	31°c/sunn y	19°c/light rain	24°c/fog	29°c/passin g cloud	28°c/pa ssing cloud
12:00pm-12:20pm	150	140	160	110	130	120	110
12:20pm-12:40pm	170	160	180	130	150	140	102
12:40pm-01:00pm	190	170	200	150	160	170	136
Total	510	470	540	390	440	430	348

Evening peak hour							
	28°c/cloudy	30°c/cloudy	29°c/clou dy	21°c/light rain	26°c/haz e	29°c/Sunny	26°c/su nny
05:00pm-05:20pm	491	400	396	302	561	330	322
05:20pm-05:40pm	361	403	500	433	600	389	415
05:40pm-06:00pm	726	668	898	445	880	415	700
Total	1578	1468	1794	1180	2041	1134	1435

Date: 03rd - 09th June 2024

(Week 6)

Jiangshe 2nd Road

Weekdays

Weekends

Morning peak hour							
Weather	21°c/cloudy	22°c/cloudy	19°c/cloudy	20°c/fog	24°c/clea r	25°c/s unny	27°c/Fair
Time interval	Mon.	Tue.	Wed.	Thurs.	Fri.	Sat.	Sun.
7:00am-7:20am	339	350	304	294	350	200	206

7:20am-7:40am	354	300	328	352	339	199	220
7:40 am-8:00 am	438	380	303	382	357	215	187
Total	1131	1030	935	1028	1046	614	613
Off-peak hour							
	26 ^o c/cloud	26 ^o c/haze	20 ^o c/light rain	25 ^o c/cloudy	26 ^o c/clou dy	31 ^o c/cl ousy	33 ^o c/cloud y
12:00pm-12:20pm	200	190	180	199	185	215	200
12:20pm-12:40pm	210	200	190	210	200	205	198
12:40pm-01:00pm	205	195	185	206	220	204	220
Total	615	585	555	615	605	624	618
Evening peak hour							
	25 ^o c/cloudy	22 ^o c/sunny	21 ^o c/light rain	27 ^o c/cloudy	27 ^o c/sun ny	31 ^o c/s unny	34 ^o c/sunn y
05:00pm-05:20pm	300	299	276	330	350	289	210
05:20pm-05:40pm	315	288	289	300	390	297	230
05:40pm-06:00pm	305	400	387	308	410	324	387
Total	920	987	952	938	1150	910	827

Appendix B

Table B1 Correlation Analysis

		TOD	PAR	WTH
TOD	Pearson Correlation	1	.229**	.050
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.487
	N	199	199	199
PAR	Pearson Correlation	.229**	1	.597**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		.000
	N	199	199	199
WTH	Pearson Correlation	.050	.597**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.487	.000	
	N	199	199	199

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table B2 Multiple Regression Analysis Result

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.629 ^a	.396	.390	.43389

a. Predictors: (Constant), WTH, TOD

b. Dependent Variable: PAR

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.172	2	12.086	64.197	.000 ^b
	Residual	36.900	196	.188		
	Total	61.072	198			

a. Dependent Variable: PAR

b. Predictors: (Constant), WTH, TOD

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	-.163	.171		-.954	.341
	TOD	.181	.051	.200	3.590	.000
	WTH	.794	.075	.587	10.556	.000

a. Dependent Variable: PAR

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	.9941	2.8020	1.6918	.34940	199
Residual	-1.25231	1.19595	.00000	.43170	199
Std. Predicted Value	-1.997	3.178	.000	1.000	199
Std. Residual	-2.886	2.756	.000	.995	199

a. Dependent Variable: PAR